

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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APPLICATION OF MODERN INFORMATION SYSTEMS IN THE ASSESSMENT OF THE TECHNICAL CONDITION OF THE EQUIPMENT OF ELECTRICAL ENERGY NETWORKS

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Abstract: This article presents the task of assessing the technical condition of electrical network equipment in power plants and substations based on the analysis of the life cycle of electrical network equipment performed. The task of determining the state of electrical network equipment as well as technical diagnostics and condition assessment has been considered as the initial minimum set of various data that ensures sufficient reliability. The use of new technologies is necessary in order to qualitatively and quantitatively assess the technical condition of electrical network equipment based on the analysis of the type of situation that occurs in electrical energy. To assess the state of the equipment of power plants and substations of electrical networks, a monitoring system of the Bayesian method was used using a complex of hardware and software.

Key words: power plants, substation, power supply system, insulation, transformer, diagnostics, expert system, automation, transformer, monitoring system, mobile portable motor, dielectric.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada elektr stansiyalari va podstantsiyalardagi elektr tarmoqlari uskunalarning texnik holatini bajarilgan elektr tarmog'i uskunalarning hayot aylanishini tahlil qilish asosida baholash vazifasi ko'rsatilgan. Elektr tarmog'i uskunasi holatini aniqlash, shuningdek, texnik diagnostika va holatni baholash vazifasi etarlicha ishonchlilikni ta'minlaydigan turli xil ma'lumotlarning dastlabki minimal to'plami sifatida ko'rib chiqildi. Yangi texnologiyalardan foydalanish elektr energiyasida yuzaga keladigan vaziyatning turini tahlil qilish asosida elektr tarmog'i uskunasi texnik holatini sifat va miqdoriy jihatdan baholash uchun zarurdir. Elektr stansiyalari va elektr tarmoqlari podstantsiyalari jihozlarning holatini baholash uchun apparat va dasturiy ta'minot majmuasidan foydalangan holda Bayes usulidagi monitoring tizimi qo'llanildi.

Kalit so'zlar: elektr stansiyalari, podstansiya, elektr ta'minoti tizimi, izolyatsiya, transformator, diagnostika, ekspert tizimi, avtomatlashtirish, transformator, monitoring tizimi, mobil ko'chma dvigatel, dielektrik.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена задача оценки технического состояния электросетевого оборудования электростанций и подстанций на основе анализа жизненного цикла выполненного электросетевого оборудования. Задача определения состояния электросетевого оборудования, а также техническая диагностика и оценка состояния рассматриваются как исходный минимальный набор различных данных, обеспечивающий достаточную достоверность. Использование новых технологий необходимо для качественной и количественной оценки технического состояния электросетевого оборудования на основе анализа типа ситуации, возникающей в электроэнергетике. Для оценки состояния оборудования электростанций и подстанций электрических сетей использована система мониторинга байесовского метода с использованием комплекса аппаратно-программных средств.

Ключевые слова: электростанции, подстанция, система электроснабжения, изоляция, трансформатор, диагностика, экспертная система, автоматизация, трансформатор, система мониторинга, мобильный переносной двигатель, диэлектрик.

INTRODUCTION

Today, issues of assessing the state of electrical equipment in power plants and substations are becoming more relevant. This, in turn, is due to the fact that a significant part of the basic electrical network equipment has developed a specified Park resource or a service life established by regulatory documents and is used within its capabilities [1] ..., [2].

The power supply system is a set of electrical installations designed to supply electricity to consumers [3]. It contains voltage networks above 1 kV and 1 kV connected by transformer substations.

Monitoring is used using a complex of hardware and software to assess the state of the equipment of power plants and substations of electrical networks. Such a complex is designed to register various information about the parameters of equipment and its structural elements, the conditions of their operation, etc., as well as to analyze the condition of the equipment based on the data obtained.

It should be noted that the cost of the basic equipment monitoring system is about 5-8% of the cost of the electrical network object. Given the decrease in costs associated with planned and emergency equipment repairs, the payment period of such systems does not exceed five years [4].

However, even with such a payment period and an average average average cost, the economic possibility of installing a monitoring system on each substation facility is often absent (substations in small towns or villages). A good alternative to the monitoring subsystem associated with assessing the condition of electrical network equipment in such cases can be any information available about the technical diagnostics and test data analysis system and/or electrical network equipment received during its operation.

In the diagnostic process, there are different definitions for monitoring electrical equipment.

In this article, it is advisable to use the definition of diagnostics as an intellectual group of consistent data, which includes statistics of values and trends (changes) that are then processed by the expert system in order to provide accurate information about the state of the equipment and the recommended measures. Monitoring can be defined as the accumulation of basic information.

The main purpose of technical diagnostics is, first of all, to recognize the state of the object in conditions of limited information and, as a result, to assess the residual resources of the system (equipment) and increase its reliability [5]. Different technical systems have different structures and goals, so the same technical diagnostics cannot be applied to all systems.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

J. Wang et al.[6] study analyzes the evolution of intelligent algorithms for transformer condition assessment. The study covers DGA, sulfur gases and other online monitoring signal sources, as well as information fusion methods for data integration and error reduction. The authors show the strengths and weaknesses of the algorithms using statistical analysis, classifiers, data fusion and uncertainty model; as a result, big-data and AI-based assessment schemes make transformer CBM (condition-based maintenance) more effective.

H. Zhi et al.[7] paper proposes a real-time digital-twin system for distribution networks: this system includes a robust state-estimation and a deep learning-based bad-data identification module. The authors demonstrate the accuracy and latency of the proposed approach in detecting and correcting incorrect/missing data by testing scenarios through a simulation platform. Conclusion: Digital twin and advanced state estimation are reliable tools for assessing the condition of network equipment.

A systematic review by J. Heluany and V. Gkioulos[8] provides a comprehensive overview of the application of digital twin technology in the power sector (generation and distribution). The authors consider the issues of DT architecture, two-way communication, virtual models and services, and security and stakeholders. As a result, the highest potential of DT is identified mainly for control and fault diagnosis in the distribution process, but the lack of specific security studies for DT itself is noted.

In the study by J. Garcia et al.[9], a review of the NLP-assisted literature analyzes signal-processing, hybrid models, and practical challenges in the field of condition-monitoring and predictive maintenance of industrial equipment. The authors show in which cases ML/DL methods work best, the possibilities of IoT and big-data integration, and the need for XAI (explainable AI). Conclusion: Combined signal-based approaches and interpretable models are effective in assessing power grid equipment.

M.Ismaeil[10] proposes an asset information model (AIMM) based on the integration of GIS and BIM, demonstrating the possibilities of combining infrastructure and equipment data into a centralized repo (spatial+non-spatial). The study shows through a practical example — asset management in campus facilities — that GIS/BIM/SCADA integration creates the necessary information base for assessing the technical condition of equipment and optimizing maintenance processes. This approach is an important infrastructure for assessing the condition in power grid asset management.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In carrying out this research work, methods widely used in scientific research methodology were used. In the process of scientific analysis, these scientific research methods were widely used, in particular, observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, and in analysis, synthesis and analysis methods were widely used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In this work, the monitoring system is understood as an assessment of the technical condition of the main electrical equipment, without taking into account the subsystems of system-wide controls (relay protection and anti-accident automation, emergency recording and electrical quality control processes, etc.).

Of course, the monitoring system has a number of technical advantages over the technical Diagnostic Data Analysis System:

- the ability to diagnose electrical appliances under the voltage of the circuit;
- control of the actual state of the equipment at the speed of the process of the circuit;
- high reliability of outputs;
- the ability to store output data (parameters and characteristics of equipment), which allows you to determine the relationship and relationship between events [11].

For example, in terms of assessing the state of electrical equipment to determine the integral assessment of the state of substations, the monitoring system has a number of disadvantages:

- very rarely does a monitoring system contain a comprehensive set of data on all electrical equipment of an existing object. It is aimed at monitoring the main components-power transformers, switching (less often – auxiliary) equipment;
- output data is a set of data on which analysis and processing form a separate problem, the solution of which requires an appropriate mathematical apparatus with the implementation of software.
- In addition, there must be certain conditions for the installation of a monitoring system in power plants and substations:
 - the equipment should have a relatively high price;
 - in the event of a failure of such equipment, the approximate damage caused by low discharge of electricity should be noticeable;
 - diagnostic testing of such equipment under load is not carried out quickly and reliably using mobile portable devices and requires significantly more expensive diagnostic equipment [12]. For example, analyzing the state of hydraulic units when it is necessary to ensure simultaneous control of temperature, electrical, mechanical and other parameters.

It follows from the above that the use of monitoring systems for each unit of electrical network equipment is not technically and economically justified, for example, in transitions carried out using simplified schemes, and even more so in grid and dead substations. But since it is necessary to analyze the technical condition of all objects of the electrical network complex, this work proposes a system based on the analysis of technical diagnostic data as a system for assessing the technical condition of electrical network equipment of power plants and substations and any available information about electrical network equipment obtained during the operation of this equipment.

Today, technical diagnostic methods (based on non-destructive testing methods) and tests are actively used to assess the condition of electrical equipment in power plants and substations.

The frequency and size of equipment diagnostics and testing are regulated. The number, type, meaning and methods of data collection are different and depend on the diagnostic method and the purpose of the equipment [13].

For almost any type of equipment, there is at least one non-destructive testing method, with which it is possible to obtain information about the condition of the equipment with a frequency of control at least once a year. According to the general classification, all methods of diagnostics of electrical equipment and its control can be divided into two groups:

- non-destructive testing methods that do not require the destruction of samples of test materials (products) of the circuit;
- destructive control methods that require the destruction of samples of test materials (products).

All methods of non-destructive control can be distinguished on the basis of the physical phenomena on which they are based. The following non-destructive testing methods are most commonly used for electrical equipment:

- magnetic of the moment;
- electric in the wind;

- circuit current;
- radio waves of the moment;
- heat of the moment;
- optical;
- radiation;
- solo acoustic;
- penetrating substances (capillary and leakage).

Within each species, methods are also classified according to additional characteristics.

Consider the definitions for each unbreakable testing method used in regulatory documents.

Definitions for each non-perturbative test method used in regulatory documents include based on the determination of magnetic properties.

Magnetic control methods are based on recording the magnetic scattering fields that occur on defects or determining the magnetic properties of the controlled products.

Electrical control methods, in accordance, are based on recording the parameters of the electric field that interact with the control object, or the area that appears on the controlled object as a result of external influence.

The method of radio wave control is based on the analysis of the interaction of the radio wave range with the control object of electromagnetic radiation.

Thermal control methods, in accordance, are based on recording the thermal fields of the control object.

Visually, optical control methods are based on the interaction of optical radiation with the control object.

Radiation control methods are based on recording and analyzing penetrating ionizing radiation after interacting with a controlled object.

Acoustic control methods are based on the application of excited elastic vibrations at the control object.

Capillary control methods are based, accordingly, on the capillary penetration of indicator fluids into the surface and continuous spaces of the material of the object of observation and registration of indicator traces formed visually or using a transducer.

It should be noted that according to the regulatory framework for analyzing the state of electrical network equipment, all these methods are not mandatory, some of them are recommended.

Mandatory includes the following test methods:

- measuring the DC resistance and suction coefficient of insulation;
- measurement of insulation properties: dielectric loss angle tangent, insulation capacity;
- high voltage insulation test;
- oil Test (physico-chemical analysis);
- assessment of the moisture content of solid insulation, etc.

Assessment of the application and effectiveness of modern information systems.

The system developed in this article is positioned as an expert system for assessing the oil-filled state of equipment of various electrical networks. Therefore, the greatest interest of the existing expert systems is the diagnostic+ system, which is designed to analyze the state of almost any substation equipment.

The method of Bayes' theorem is to calculate the conditional probability. The traditional method of calculating conditional probability (the probability that an event will occur when another event occurs) is to use the conditional probability formula, calculate the probability that the first and second event will occur simultaneously, and divide it by the probability that the second event will occur.

When calculating the conditional probability by Bayes' theorem, you use the following steps:

Considering condition A to be true, one can determine the probability that condition B is true.

To determine the probability that a phenomenon is true.

Multiply two probabilities together.

To be in the probability of event B occurring.

This means that the formula of Bayes' theorem can be expressed as follows:

$$P\left(\frac{A}{B}\right) = P\left(\frac{B}{A}\right) \times \frac{P(A)}{P(B)} \quad (1)$$

Calculating a conditional probability like this is especially useful when the inverse conditional probability can be easily calculated, or when calculating the joint probability is very difficult.

In this process, the state of the power transformer was analyzed based on technical diagnostic data to assess the possibility of implementing the system using the Bayesian method, such as the "Diagnostic+" System [14].

Using the Bayesian method, the state of the D_i object associated with this state and the k_i factor can be expressed as the probability of the manifestation of the factor and the probability of the state:

$$P\left(\frac{D_i}{k_i}\right) = P(D_i) \frac{P\left(\frac{k_i}{D_i}\right)}{P(k_i)}, \quad (2)$$

here is the D_i probability of manifestation of the k_i factor in an object in the $P\left(\frac{k_i}{D_i}\right)$ state;
 $P(D_i)$ - D_i aprior probability of State;

$P(k_i)$ - k_i the aprior probability of the manifestation of the factor in any object;

$P\left(\frac{D_i}{k_i}\right)$ - k_i the posterior probability of the D_i state in the manifestation of the factor.

The basic idea of the Bayesian method is to evaluate the probabilistic properties of determining the state of $P\left(\frac{D_i}{k_i}\right)$ based on the factors available for analysis.

In sequential consideration of different combinations of factors, an increase in the value of $P\left(\frac{D_i}{k_i}\right)$ indicates a high probability of the D_i event, while a decrease indicates its practical impossibility.

To determine the state of an oil transformer with a voltage of 110 kv, it is advisable to include a classification of electrical equipment States. Table 1 included four positions depending on whether the indicator's condition is consistent with its condition, or whether there is a defect (Table 1) [15], ..., [16].

Table 1. Possible cases of equipment

Position	The indicator is in the normal range	The presence of a flaw
D_1	Yes	No
D_2	Yes	Yes
D_3	No	Yes
D_4	No	No

Next, with the help of expert assessments, the Apriori probabilities of the initial cases are determined.

We believe that the characters are independent. In this case, the state of the power transformer K is characterized by a set of independent characters, each of which has two outputs:

$$K = (k_1, k_2), \quad (3)$$

where k_1 is a manifestation of the K Property, and k_2 is an invisibility.

Below (Figure 1), the probability of manifestation and/or invisibility can be expressed in terms of distribution functions. The figure shows the functions of manifestation of status symbols: $D_1 - \mu_1(x), D_2 - \mu_2(x), D_3 - \mu_3(x)$ va $D_4 - \mu_4(x)$, they can be defined in the range $X = \{0 \dots 3\}$.

The value of an independent variable describes the level of the state of the object of study.

Figure 1. Functions of distribution of manifestations of state signs.

Generalized linear representations of strong $\mu_1(x)$ and normal $\mu_2(x)$ properties give probabilistic properties of the manifestation of some character of $\mu_p(x)$, while generalized linear representations of weak manifestation functions of $\mu_2(x)$ and its absence give the probabilistic properties of $\mu_4(x)$ non-representation $\mu_N(x)$ symbols.

The characteristic functions of $\mu_p(x)$ and $\mu_N(x)$ allow determining the distribution of the probability of manifestation of signs for a given D_i diagnosis (Fig. 2). For each case of the object of study described in table 2, similar functions should be identified in all signs of diagnosis.

The probability of any state that can occur with different combinations of symbols can be determined by the Bayesian formula:

$$P\left(\frac{D_i}{K}\right) = \frac{P(D_i)P\left(\frac{K}{D_i}\right)}{\sum_{s=1}^n P(D_s)P\left(\frac{K}{D_s}\right)}, \tag{4}$$

where, $K - \{k_1, k_2, k_3, \dots, k_n\}$ is a set of two-level characters in;
 n-number of case diagnoses;

Initial probability of diagnosis of $P(D_i)$ point D_i ;

$P\left(\frac{K}{D_i}\right)$ is the probability of the manifestation of signs determined according to the expression in the diagnosis of D_i :

$$P\left(\frac{K}{D_i}\right) = P\left(\frac{k_1}{D_i}\right)P\left(\frac{k_2}{D_i}\right) \dots P\left(\frac{k_v}{D_i}\right), \tag{5}$$

where, $K - \{k_1, k_2, k_3, \dots, k_v\}$ a set of two-level characters in the composition.

Such an analysis makes it possible to obtain a quantitative description of the combination of symptoms of a diagnosed condition depending on a particular case.

For analysis of dissolved gas analysis in the garden of fat is carried out for gas xromatografik seven (3-table): meta (CH_4), carbon dioxide (CO_2), etilen (C_2H_4), acetyl (C_2H_2), back etan (C_2H_6), hydrogen (H_2), carbon oxide (CO).

Figure 2. Characteristic functions of the manifestation of probability of properties.

To confirm the studies carried out, a data-based calculation of the probability of cases was carried out. Chromatographic analysis using the appropriate functions, the dissolved gases of the power transformer, as well as the probability of the manifestation and invisibility of the signs for each gas, are calculated separately.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This article presents multi-criterion tasks of decision-making in conditions of limited information, the task of assessing the technical condition of power plants and electrical network equipment in the substation, based on the analysis of the life cycle of electrical network equipment performed. As an initial minimum set of data that ensures sufficient reliability, it will be necessary to determine the state of electrical network equipment as well as perform technical diagnostics.

It is necessary to create new tools for a qualitative and quantitative assessment of the technical condition of electrical network equipment based on the analysis of the situation that has arisen in electricity. It carries out a state analysis based on any collected data on the object of research, taking into account operational experience, and on this basis consists in determining decisions on the further operation of the equipment [17], ..., [19].

LIST OF USED LITERATURES:

1. МРСК Урала. Годовой отчет 2012 [Электронный ресурс]: офиц. сайт. – Режим доступа: <http://report2012.mrsk-ural.ru/reports/mrskural/annual/2012/gb/Russian/9030.html>. – Загл. с экрана (дата обращения 05.01.2015).
2. Россети. Годовой отчет 2009 год [Электронный ресурс]: офиц. сайт. – Режим доступа: <http://www.rosseti.ru/investors/info/year/>. – Загл. с экрана (дата обращения 05.01.2015).
3. Черноусова, Л.В., Электрические станции и подстанции: учебнометодические рекомендации по выполнению курсового проекта для обучающихся по направлению подготовки 13.03.02 «Электроэнергетика и электротехника» / Л.В.Черноусова. - Черкесск: БИЦ СевКавГГТА, 2017. -40 с.
4. Галкин В. С. Вопросы проектирования автоматизированных систем мониторинга электрооборудования на подстанциях 500–220 кВ с учетом обеспечения надежности электрических сетей / В. С. Галкин, Т. М. Лангборт, В. А. Липаткин, В. А. Смирнов // Электрические станции. – 2006. – № 7. – С. 66–67
5. Спарлинг Б. Д. Повышение уровня мониторинга и диагностики для оптимизации передачи и распределения электроэнергии в целях улучшения финансовых показателей / Б. Д. Спарлинг // Методы и средства оценки состояния энергетического оборудования / под ред. А. И. Таджибаева, В. Н. Осотова. – СПб., 2005. – Вып. 28. – С. 178–202.
6. Wang, J., Zhang, X., Zhang, F., Wan, J., Kou, L., & Ke, W. (2022). Review on Evolution of Intelligent Algorithms for Transformer Condition Assessment. *Frontiers in Energy Research*, 10.
7. Zhi, H., Mao, R., Hao, L., Chang, X., Guo, X., & Ji, L. (2024). Digital Twin for Modern Distribution Networks by Improved State Estimation with Consideration of Bad Date Identification. *Electronics*, 13(18), 3613.
8. Heluany, J. B., & Gkioulos, V. (2023). A review on digital twins for power generation and distribution. *International Journal of Information Security*, 23, 1171–1195.
9. Garcia, J., Rios-Colque, L., Peña, A., & Rojas, L. (2025). Condition Monitoring and Predictive Maintenance in Industrial Equipment: An NLP-Assisted Review of Signal Processing, Hybrid Models, and Implementation Challenges. *Applied Sciences*, 15(10), 5465.
10. Ismaeil, E. M. H. (2024). Asset Information Model Management-Based GIS/BIM Integration in Facility Management Contract. *Sustainability*, 16(6), 2495.

11. Давиденко И. В. Структура экспертно-диагностической и информационной системы оценки состояния высоковольтного оборудования / И. В. Давиденко, В. П. Голубев, В. И. Комаров, В. Н. Осотов // Электрические станции: ежемесячный производственно-технический журнал. - 1997. - N 6. - С. 25-27.
12. Давиденко И. В. Структура экспертно-диагностической и информационной системы оценки состояния высоковольтного оборудования / И. В. Давиденко, В. П. Голубев, В. И. Комаров, В. Н. Осотов // Электрические станции: ежемесячный производственно-технический журнал. - 1997. - N 6. - С. 25-27.
13. Россети. Годовой отчет 2009 год [Электронный ресурс]: офиц. сайт. – Режим доступа: <http://www.rosseti.ru/investors/info/year/>. – Загл. С экрана (дата обращения 05.01.2015).
14. Хальясмаа А. И. Оценка состояния силовых трансформаторов на основе анализа данных технической диагностики / А. И. Хальясмаа, С. А. Дмитриев, С. Е. Кокин, М. В. Осотова // Вестник ЮУрГУ. – 2013. – Том 13. – №2. – С. 114–12.
15. M. A. Sobirov, I. S. Kurbanova, S. I. Hamrayeva and Z. O. Sabirova, "Analysis of Mathematical Modeling Model in Power Supply Systems," 2023 IEEE XVI International Scientific and Technical Conference Actual Problems of Electronic Instrument Engineering (APEIE), Novosibirsk, Russian Federation, 2023, pp. 1570-1573, doi: 10.1109/APEIE59731.2023.10347687.
16. M. A. Sobirov, I. S. Kurbanova and Z. O. Sabirova, "Multi-Level Approach in Organizing the Energy Supply System in Telecommunication Networks," 2023 IEEE XVI International Scientific and Technical Conference Actual Problems of Electronic Instrument Engineering (APEIE), Novosibirsk, Russian Federation, 2023, pp. 1830-1834, doi: 10.1109/APEIE59731.2023.10347846.
17. Ertem G., Çelik B. and Yeşilyurt S., 2008. Endüstriyel tav fırınlarında ısı dengliği hesaplamaları ve enerji verimliliğinin belirlenmesi. IV. Ege Enerji Sempozyumu, İzmir, Turkey, pp. 1–8.
18. Manatura K. and Tangtrakul M., 2010. A study of specific energy consumption in reheating furnace using regenerative burners combined with recuperator. Silpakorn U Science & Tech J 4(2), 7–13.
19. Terzi Ü.K. and Baykal R., 2011. Efficient and effective use of energy: A case study of Tofas. Environmental Research, Engineering and Management 1(55), 29–33.

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